

Numerical Evaluation of the Effect of Gypsum Panels as Infill Walls in Reinforced Concrete Frame Structures

Ornela Şen*^{ORCID}, Kostandina Zaçi^{ORCID}

Polis University., Dept. of Architecture and Engineering, Tirana, Albania

*Corresponding author: ornela_sen@universitetipolis.edu.al

Abstract

Gypsum is an abundant and environmentally friendly material which has been increasingly used in the construction industry for non-structural purposes such as partition walls and ceiling systems. Traditional infill/partition walls are commonly constructed with bricks or concrete blocks, which result in somewhat stiff partition walls. The brick/block walls are often damaged by seismic events, and in some cases they even collapse, which causes life and economic losses. Gypsum board panel partition walls generally come at an initial higher cost, but also have some advantages, such as good thermal and acoustic insulation, fire resistance, lightness and ease of assembly. The structural behavior of gypsum board panel partition walls has not been investigated though. They are expected to have a somewhat positive impact or a lesser negative impact on structures during earthquakes, due to their lightness. This paper aimed to initiate a discussion on this topic by assessing the contribution of the gypsum partition walls to the structural response of RC structures. This was done by evaluating five wall material/modeling scenarios and comparing the results. Two of the scenarios used brick walls, once modeled as loads and once modeled as compression struts. The rest of the scenarios used gypsum walls once modeled as loads and then as compression struts of different widths. The results of the study indicate that the contribution of gypsum walls to the structural behavior of RC frames is insignificant and can be safely neglected during the structural design process.

Keywords: gypsum panels, infill walls, partition walls, nonlinear analysis, RC frames

Introduction

Gypsum is a chalk like white powder that has found a wide array of applications in construction. It is abundant in nature, and it is also a common by-product of several industrial processes, particularly the fertilizers industry. Since it is a byproduct of an existing industry, it has a much smaller carbon footprint than cement, and it makes for an environmentally friendly alternative to the traditional binders [1]. On the other hand, gypsum has some very desirable properties. Junior et al., [2] reported that gypsum panel walls provided very good sound insulation at lower densities than other comparable construction materials. Losso and Viveiros [3] pointed out that it was crucial to provide proper filling materials between the plasterboards to obtain the desired acoustic insulation. Neuberger et al., [4] reported that while the thermal conductivity of gypsum block as an untreated material is the same as the thermal conductivity of typical brick walls, this conductivity is greatly reduced when gypsum is used in combination with other materials, or when air pores are introduced. Thermal conductivity affects the behavior of gypsum boards under the threat of fire as well. When gypsum as a material is subjected to increasingly high temperatures, it shrinks and cracks, thus affecting the stability of whatever element is constructed with it. However, the use of other materials, such as fibers can delay the formation of cracks and can yield towards nonlinear behavior at high temperatures [5].

Evaluating the mechanical properties of gypsum is a more complex topic. Since gypsum is often used as wall panels, supported on timber or metallic frames, and filled in between with insulating materials, the wall panel properties will be highly dependent on the configuration of these components. Nonetheless some attempts were made to identify the mechanical properties of gypsum as a material [5, 6]. Schoenwald et al., [7] addresses this difficulty and report that the stud spacing is one of the decisive parameters in the mechanical properties of gypsum wall panels. Rahmanian reported that the compression strength of gypsum boards is considerably higher than their tensile strength [5].

Infill walls made of brittle materials are commonly used in reinforced concrete buildings as perimeter and partition walls. The infill walls are somewhat rigid and very brittle non-structural components which often times have proved problematic during seismic events. Traditional brick infill walls can increase the strength and the stiffness of the structures [8, 9]. They also change the behavior and failure mechanisms [10] and introduce failure modes such as soft story [11] and short column [12]. The increase in strength and stiffness of the RC frames from the traditional brick infill walls comes with other shortfalls such as reduced ductility and energy dissipation [13] and considerable strength and stiffness degradation after the failure of the walls [14].

In the last years the use of gypsum panels as partition walls has surged for a variety of reasons. Besides the good acoustic and thermal insulating properties, gypsum walls are very lightweight, and they are easy to install. They require far less time and workmanship to install, when compared to brick infill walls. From the functionality and cost perspective, gypsum walls are more advantageous than brick infill walls. However, non-structural elements are known to affect the seismic performance of structures [15, 16]. Besides, in many cases during seismic events, the failure of non-structural elements is the main cause of fatalities [17]. Gypsum walls, being lightweight, are expected to have a lesser negative impact on the structures than brick infill walls.

Since the use of gypsum panels and gypsum boards is gaining momentum as partition walls, this study aims to investigate if these panels have any contribution in the structural soundness of the buildings or not. If gypsum panels do not provide any strength or stiffness contribution to the structure, they still improve the overall building behavior by reducing the seismic weight. If gypsum panels provide any strength and stiffness to the structure further studies are required to investigate in detail how it will affect the behavior of structures and whether it introduces ductile or brittle mechanisms and failure modes.

This comparison will be carried out on small 3D frames with one story and one bay in both directions. The frames were designed according to Eurocode 2 [18] and Eurocode 8 [19]. Three scenarios were considered. In the first scenario, the frame was designed with no infill walls of any type at all. In the second and third scenarios, the frame was designed with brick and gypsum infill walls respectively. The infill wall was modeled as a compression strut for both these two scenarios [20, 21]. The effect of the infill walls, particularly the gypsum infills on the fundamental period, interstory drift ratios, initial stiffness, and lateral load capacity were observed and compared for all the models.

The Study

A three-story model with one bay in each direction was designed to implement and test the gypsum infill models. This frame had a simple plan with dimensions 6x4 m centerline-to-centerline of the columns. The story height is 3.1 m. In the brick wall model, a uniformly distributed load of 9 kN/m was applied on the beams of the 1st and 2nd stories to represent the brick infill walls. In the gypsum wall models, a uniformly distributed load of 1 kN/m was applied on the beams of the 1st and 2nd stories to represent the gypsum infill walls. C30/37 and S500 were used to model the material properties of the constituents of reinforced concrete. The frame was designed according to Eurocode 2 and Eurocode 8, using PGA=0.3g and soil class D. Table 1 and Table 2 contain the cross-sectional details of the beams and columns for the models with brick and gypsum infill walls respectively.

Table 1. Cross-section sizes and reinforcement ratios for the model with brick infills

Structural elements	Cross-section dimensions (cm)	Reinforcement ratios (%) by floor		
		1	2	3
Columns	60x40	3.16	1.77	1.00
Beams (x-dir./long direction)	30x60	1.89	1.49	0.75
Beams (y-dir./short direction)	30x60	2.21	1.45	0.65

Table 2. Cross-section sizes and reinforcement ratios for the model with gypsum infills

Structural elements	Cross-section dimensions (cm)	Reinforcement ratios (%) by floor		
		1	2	3
Columns	60x40	2.50	1.50	1.00
Beams (x-dir./long direction)	30x60	1.46	1.23	0.65
Beams (y-dir./short direction)	30x60	1.68	1.21	0.65

An FE model was created in SAP2000 [22] using frame elements for the beams and the columns, and shell elements for the slabs. The nonlinear behavior of the frame members was modeled with plastic hinges. The FEMA 356 hinge models [23] were used in this study. Both brick masonry and gypsum are brittle materials. During seismic events, they are loaded in compression along their diagonal. Therefore, compressions struts are a suitable approach for nonlinear analyses that uses the frame and bar element approach. FEMA 356 defines the compression strut width as given by Equations 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows the FEMA 356 schematic representation of the compression strut.

$$a_d = 0.175(\lambda_d h_c)^{-0.4} r_d \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda_d = \left[\frac{E_d t_d \sin 2\theta}{4E_c I_k H_w} \right]^{0.25} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. The FEMA 356 formulation for the equivalent compression strut

However, Movahednia et al. [6] suggested a revised formulation for the width of the compression strut of gypsum infill walls, based on a parametric study. This formulation is presented in Equation 3. This new equation presents a reduced numerical coefficient for the base FEMA 356 equation presented in Equation 1.

$$a_d = 0.086(\lambda_d h_c)^{-0.4} r_d \quad (3)$$

The capacity of the infill compression struts was calculated using the formulation for the maximum force capacity from Zarnic and Gostic [24], as shown in Equations 4 and 5.

$$F_m = 0.818 \frac{f_{tp} L_w t_w}{c_1} \left(1 + \sqrt{c_1^2 + 1} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$c_1 = 1.925 \frac{L_w}{H_w} \quad (5)$$

A total of 5 models were considered:

- BL – the nonlinear model of the frame with the brick walls modeled as loads
- BS – the nonlinear model of the frame with the brick walls modeled as compression struts
- GL – the nonlinear model of the frame with the gypsum walls modeled as loads
- GS – the nonlinear model of the frame with the gypsum walls modeled as compression struts
- GSR – similar to model GS, but the width of the equivalent strut is reduced per relevant literature

Results and Discussions

For these five models the following parameters were investigated: the seismic weight, the fundamental period, the capacity curves and the interstory drift ratios. The seismic weight was calculated as $1.0 \times DL + 0.3 \times LL$. The seismic weight of the brick wall models was calculated to be 1369.2 kN, while the seismic weight of the gypsum wall models was calculated to be 1049.2 kN. The difference in seismic weight is due to the lighter weight of the gypsum walls. The dynamic properties of all five models are

displayed in Table 3. It was observed that the periods of the model with gypsum wall were very similar, with a difference of 2%. The periods of the gypsum wall models were also very similar to the period of the BL model (the model with brick walls that were applied as loads only). The difference between the period of the BL and BS model was about 10%. Since in both BL and BS models the infill walls were modeled as loads only, this difference in fundamental period is completely attributed to the difference in seismic weight.

Table 3. Dynamic properties of the models

Model	T1 (s)	T2 (s)	T3 (s)
BL	0.389	0.357	0.350
BS	0.163	0.136	0.129
GL	0.353	0.328	0.320
GS	0.341	0.311	0.308
GSR	0.347	0.319	0.314

The capacity curves in both directions are displayed in Figure 2. It was observed that the gypsum wall models had very similar capacity curves, and very similar initial stiffness and base shear capacities regardless of the way the brick walls were modeled. In the brick wall models, the modeling strategy played an important role. The frame with brick walls modeled as loads only behaved very similarly to the gypsum wall models. This modeling strategy is the strategy commonly used during the design process of RC structures. The frame with brick walls modeled as compression struts displayed considerably higher initial stiffness, greater base shear capacity and more brittle behavior. This modeling strategy is a good simulator of the actual behavior of brick infilled frames during seismic events. Therefore, it was observed that while for the brick infilled frames the modeling strategy affected the capacity and behavior of the frames, for the gypsum infilled frames the modeling strategy had little effect on either capacity or behavior.

Figure 2. Capacity curves of all models (a) loading direction x; (b) loading direction y

The investigation of the interstory drift ratios yielded similar conclusions. The values of the interstory drift ratios are almost identical for models GL, GS and GSR. The BL model has slightly higher interstory drift ratios, while the BS model has considerably smaller drift ratios than the rest of the models. From the investigation of the period, weight, capacity curves and interstory drift ratios it was observed that:

- There is a difference in capacity and stiffness between the BL and BS models. This is expected because in the BL model only the weight of the brick infill walls is included, while in the BS models the weight, the stiffness and the capacity of the brick infill walls was included. Brick infill walls are relatively stiff and strong, and their contribution to the capacity and stiffness of the frames should not be neglected.
- There is almost no difference in capacity and stiffness between the GL, GS and GSR models. While the GL model includes only the weight of the gypsum walls, while the GS and GSR

models include the strength and stiffness of the of the gypsum walls as well, the small differences indicate a very small contribution of the gypsum infill walls to the strength and stiffness of the RC frames.

- There is a very small difference in capacity and stiffness between the BL model and the gypsum wall models. This slight difference is due to the greater weight of the BL model, which results in greater seismic loads and greater displacements. Therefore, the stiffness contribution of the gypsum panels is insignificant.

Figure 3. Interstory drift ratio of all the models for (a) loading direction x; (b) loading direction y

Conclusions

In this paper, the strength and stiffness contribution to the capacity of RC frames was investigated through nonlinear analyses. It was observed that gypsum infilled frames behaved differently from brick infilled frames. The gypsum infill walls had an insignificant impact on the strength and stiffness of the RC frames. Therefore, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- It is not necessary to include the contribution of strength and stiffness of the gypsum infills in the analysis and design of the gypsum wall infilled frames.
- Modeling the gypsum walls is sufficient. Therefore, the model used during the design of RC structures will match with the expected performance during seismic events.
- The same cannot be said for brick infilled frames, in which neglecting to include the strength and stiffness of the brick walls in the design will result in a different behavior during seismic events.

Therefore, gypsum walls can be very good alternatives for infill walls for RC construction. Not only do they have very good insulation properties and ease of assembly, but they also prove to be advantageous from the structural point of view. Modeling the gypsum infill walls as loads only is the simplest modeling strategy, and it is sufficient. The nonlinear analyses that were performed also indicated that the gypsum walls are less likely to be damaged during earthquakes, which is another advantage. However, due to their lightweight, even if the gypsum walls were damaged, they will be less likely to cause damage and casualties as brick infill walls do when they collapse. Finally, gypsum is a relatively clean material, which adds to the advantages of using gypsum panels as infill walls instead of brick walls.

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